

Lab Study Protocol for Secret Management Tool (SMT) Project

Expected maximum completion time: 60-70 minutes

- Environment setup for participants before research tasks
 - Email/password for cloud service account access for SMT
 - Links to SMT setup and/or help documentation
 - Personal machine setup with the following:
 - Downloaded CLI installation of SMT
 - Executable coding script with hard-coded secret
- Two research tasks
 - Store the removed hard-coded secret into the SMT web interface account, and then access the secret from the CLI
 - Securely inject the secret stored within the SMT into a running process of the executable coding script as an environment variable

General Study Flow:

1. Establish the environment setup for the participant.
2. Provide introduction and read participant rights to the participant.
 - a. The introduction will include an overview of both the study and environment setup
3. Remind participants about agreeing to being recorded visually/audio
 - a. Mention to participant they agreed via consent form
 - b. Answer any questions they might have
4. Notify the participant that the session will start being recorded.
5. If there are no further questions, provide the participant with the first study task:
 - a. First 2-3 minutes: Ask the participant a small set of warm up questions to get their prior experience with the study topic.
 - b. Next 2 minutes: Tell the participant they have to use the help documentation to store a hard-coded secret within the web interface of the SMT and then access that same secret from the CLI of the SMT {HCP Vault Secrets, Infisical, or Doppler}.
 - c. Next 25-30 minutes: Give the participant time to perform the required tasks for this portion of the session.
 - d. Next 5-10 minutes: Ask the participant about how the task felt while using the help documentation and learn about their experience interacting with both the SMT and respective help advice.
 - i. The questions within each task may not strictly follow the flow as shown in this document. Some questions may be asked or answered during task

completion or after. Also, questions asked within the wrap up section are added in case they were not addressed during the two tasks.

6. Repeat step 5 with the second study task:
 - a. First 2 minutes: Tell the participant they have to use the help documentation to inject the accessed secret into the executable coding script as an environment variable and run the file without exposing the secret.
 - b. Next 25-30 minutes: Give the participant time to perform the required tasks for this portion of the session.
 - c. Next 5-10 minutes: Ask the participant about how the task felt while using the help documentation and learn about their experience interacting with both the SMT and respective help advice.
 - i. The questions within each task may not strictly follow the flow as shown in this document. Some questions may be asked or answered during task completion or after. Also, questions asked within the wrap up section are added in case they were not addressed during the two tasks.
7. End the study with wrap up questions

Intro - Before study task

Greeting the Participant (~ 1-2 min)

Hello (participant name),

Thank you for your interest and for your time.

My name is [researcher], and I am a PhD student researcher at [Institution] in the [Institution] lab]. Today, we are going to have you complete two tasks that are aimed to see whether you can securely store, access, and inject secrets into an application with a secret management tool using its online help documentation. Secret management involves the processes developers take to manage secrets (sensitive data) such as passwords, keys, and tokens securely for their day to day operations so that secrets are not exposed. Secret management tools are services that developers or companies use to store and distribute their secrets securely across different applications, CI/CD pipelines, or third party services. Today, you will perform two secret management tasks with the secret management tool {HCP Vault Secrets, Infisical, or Doppler} and its respective help documentation which provides instructions for each task.

Our goal is to see whether or not you are able to complete each research task within a 30 minute time period using the SMT official online help documentation. In the case you reach a point where you do not feel that the official help documentation is providing enough or clear guidance on how to complete a task, you are also free to search the web for secondary help advice to complete the task. The secondary help advice can be of any format as well (e.g., documentation, video, pictures, etc...)

In order to complete the tasks, we provide the following resources:

1. Email/password credentials to access the web interface for their SMT
2. Links to web pages for official help documentation for SMT setup and configuration.
3. A local machine (laptop or macbook) with the following:
 - a. Downloaded CLI installation of SMT
 - b. Executable coding script with hard-coded secret

Once you complete each task, we will then ask you several questions about your experience for that task. We may also ask you questions during your experience as well to gauge how helpful or lacking the official help documentation or advice is towards assisting your completion. After you finish answering questions for the second task, we will ask you a couple of wrap up questions to end the session.

Lastly, feel free to ask any questions during your task completion and also think aloud during the tasks. We welcome any comments, questions, or feedback you may have towards the help advice or SMT itself.

Do you have any questions about the purpose of our study?

<Answer any questions, or continue>

Participant Rights (~1-2 min) and Initial Consent (~ 3-4 min)

Good, Before we begin, I would like to quickly go over your rights as a participant for this study. You are free to withdraw your participation at any time, not respond to a question or complete a specific task throughout this process. You will still be fully compensated up to the half hour of which you have stopped participating. You may also take a break at any time.

Do you have any questions about your rights as a participant?

<Answer any questions, or continue>

Data Collection and Anonymity (~1-2 min)

Thanks, all recordings, transcripts, and other data collected of this study analyzed pseudonymously as part of our research work and stored without reference to you or your company. You will be assigned a pseudonym such as "Participant 1" and "Company 1", which will not allow any conclusions to be drawn about you or their company.

Any information used in reports will only be used in pseudonymized form.

We may wish to use verbatim quotes from this session pseudonymized in publications or presentations. This is independent of their prior consent and participation in the study.

Do you have any questions?

<Answer any questions, or continue>

Confirm Consent (~ 1-2 min)

As we previously stated in the consent form you signed before this session, we would like to record the study and evaluate it scientifically in a pseudonymous way. Can we confirm that you still agree to be visually and audio recorded for this experiment as you stated in your consent form?

<If participant agrees, start recording and get consent on the record>

Start Study Task 1- Store a hard-coded secret within an SMT and then access the stored secret from the command line. (~30 min)

Warm-up Questions:

1. Prior experience with managing secrets:
 - a. Do you have any prior experience with managing secrets?
 - i. E.g., managing secrets for an industry role? Academic project?
 - ii. If you held prior experience:
 1. What type of secrets did you manage?
 2. Did you use any specific tools or perform specific management practices?
 - b. Can you confirm your academic and/or professional position? (e.g., your degree program and employment status)

Imagine your company has provided you with {HCP Vault Secrets, Infisical, or Doppler} as a secret management tool to use for managing secrets used for your company coding development projects. They also have provided you with the following respective help documentation to get you started using the service. Using the available help documentation, you are first tasked with performing the following:

1. **Remove the hard coded secret “CompanySecretToken” from the local python file “SecureSecret.py” [Show python file in VS Code]**

2. Store the CompanySecretToken within the App directory titled “CompanySecretStorage”. Store within the development branch. **[Show Infisical web page with account logged in already]**
3. Access the stored secret from the CLI by logging into the tool through CLI access and printing the secret in a singular line in plaintext. **[Show terminal and VS Code]**

None of these tasks require any special frameworks, functions, libraries, or services. You are just tasked with using the online help documentation, as necessary, as well as the CLI tool (already installed onto the machine) to access the tool and python file. We have provided you with VS Studio Code as well to use as a text editor. Lastly, in the case you feel that the advice provided from the tool’s website cannot help you complete this task, you are more than welcome to search the web for other help documentation, advice, or even media to help you accomplish this task.

Feel free to ask questions but also just try your best! Perfection is not a requirement!

If you do not have any further questions: please begin the task.

<Have the participant start the task>

<After Task completion, or when participant time runs out or participant stops>

Thank you for completing the first task, can you please answer a few questions?

1. Overall Experience:
 - a. How would you describe your overall experience of performing this task?
 - i. Is there anything that you did not like or find difficult for this task?
 1. Vice versa?
2. Negative emotions
 - a. Were there any parts during this task exercise where you experienced any negative emotions?
 - i. *This can include annoyance, confusion, fatigue, frustration, or any form of disapproval/dissatisfaction with either the tool, the advice you looked at, or the task itself.*
 - ii. If so, please explain why you felt those emotions.
 - b. **Also ask the participant about expressions of negative emotions and positive emotions you captured if not already mentioned by the participant.**
3. Tool Documentation Content based questions
 - a. Code snippets/examples/explanatory text
 - i. Did you experience any difficulties or challenges when using code snippets, examples, or explanatory text from the tool documentation as resources to complete the task?

1. If so, why? What made using these specific qualities of the content challenging?
 - ii. Did you experience difficulty in mentally connecting the process for what you were assigned to do in the task with how the respective content is provided in the tool documentation?
 1. *To rephrase:* Was it challenging to understand how to complete the task assigned to you as you were reading the content provided in the tool documentation?
 - a. If so, please explain
 - iii. Was there anything with the content (code snippets/examples/explanatory text) that you liked or found helpful towards completing the task?
 1. If so, please explain.
 - b. Structure and formatting of tool documentation content
 - i. Did you experience any challenges in finding the information that allowed you to complete or progress through the task?
 1. If so, please explain what challenges you faced in finding the information.
 - ii. Did the structure of the tool documentation content (e.g., section headers, usage of formatting like bullet points or lists, toolbar format, etc) present any challenges for you in finding information and completing the task?
 1. If so, please explain.
 2. Vice versa?
 - iii. Did the format of the advice content (as it relates to text, pictures, videos) present any challenges to you or make it harder to complete the task?
 1. If so, please explain.
 2. Vice versa?
4. Secondary source based questions (If they searched for external sources)
 - a. If you looked up advice from sources external to the tool documentation, why did you search for other resources?
 - i. What specifically did you look for in secondary sources that were not present and/or made clear within the help documentation?
 - b. Were there any external sources that you preferred or found more helpful towards completing the task than the tool documentation?
 - i. If so, what were these sources and why did you find them more helpful?

Start Study Task 2- Securely inject a secret from the SMT into a running application as an environment variable. (~30 min)

Now imagine that you need to test if you can run an application that needs the secret injected into it without exposing the secret into your local environment. The goal is to be

able to inject the secret stored within Infisical into an application's process at run time. The specific of the task are explained below:

- Using the help documentation, or anything else you find helpful, find a way to inject the secret as an environment variable into a process that executes the python file (version 3) you edited.

Once again, none of these tasks require any special frameworks, functions, libraries, or services. You are first recommended to use the online help documentation, and then secondary advice sources outside the tool's website if necessary. You only need the CLI tool, or VS Studio Code text editor, to run the tool and python file.

Feel free to ask questions but also just try your best! Perfection is not a requirement!

If you do not have any further questions: please begin the task.

<Have the participant start the task>

<After Task completion, or when participant time runs out or participant stops>

Thank you for completing the first task, can you please answer a few questions?

1. Overall Experience:
 - a. How would you describe your overall experience of performing this task?
 - i. Is there anything that you did not like or find difficult for this task?
 1. Vice versa?
2. Negative emotions
 - a. Were there any parts during this task exercise where you experienced any negative emotions?
 - i. This can include annoyance, confusion, fatigue, frustration, or any form of disapproval/dissatisfaction with either the tool, the advice you looked at, or the task itself.
 - ii. If so, please explain why you felt those emotions.
 - b. Also ask the participant about expressions of negative emotions and positive emotions you captured if not already mentioned by the participant.**
3. Tool Documentation Content based questions
 - a. Code snippets/examples/explanatory text
 - i. Did you experience any difficulties or challenges when using code snippets, examples, or explanatory text from the tool documentation as resources to complete the task?
 1. If so, why? What made using these specific qualities of the content challenging?

- ii. Did you experience difficulty in mentally connecting the process for what you were assigned to do in the task with how the respective content is provided in the tool documentation?
 - 1. *To rephrase:* Was it challenging to understand how to complete the task assigned to you as you were reading the content provided in the tool documentation?
 - a. If so, please explain
 - iii. Was there anything with the content (code snippets/examples/explanatory text) that you liked or found helpful towards completing the task?
 - 1. If so, please explain.
 - b. Structure and formatting of tool documentation content
 - i. Did you experience any challenges in finding the information that allowed you to complete or progress through the task?
 - 1. If so, please explain what challenges you faced in finding the information.
 - ii. Did the structure of the tool documentation content (e.g., section headers, usage of formatting like bullet points or lists, toolbar format, etc) present any challenges for you in finding information and completing the task?
 - 1. If so, please explain.
 - 2. Vice versa?
 - iii. Did the format of the advice content (as it relates to text, pictures, videos) present any challenges to you or make it harder to complete the task?
 - 1. If so, please explain.
 - 2. Vice versa?
- 4. Secondary source based questions (If they searched for external sources)
 - a. If you looked up advice from sources external to the tool documentation, why did you search for other resources?
 - i. What specifically did you look for in secondary sources that were not present and/or made clear within the help documentation?
 - b. Were there any external sources that you preferred or found more helpful towards completing the task than the tool documentation?
 - i. If so, what were these sources and why did you find them more helpful?

Wrap up (~1-3 min)

Thank you for completing or attempting to complete all two tasks for this study. We have just a couple questions left to wrap up this interview [Not all of these will be asked, some may already be answered during the previous tasks]:

- 1. Tool usability feedback based questions:
 - a. Could you see yourself using this SMT for managing secrets within your own workflow? Or for your own projects?
 - i. If not, can you please explain why not?

- ii. If yes, please explain, specifically, what features or aspects help with the adoption?
2. General tool documentation and advice questions:
 - a. Do you have any preferences for the types of sources you consult when needing assistance for technical tasks like the ones today? (including online or offline)
 - i. E.g., contacting a colleague or senior associate, using official tool/service documentation, or external advice sources like blogs or crowd Q&A sites like stack overflow?
 - b. Do you have any preferences for how you typically like to view advice from help resources? (e.g., just text, media included, etc)
 - i. If so, please explain.
3. Do you have any last comments or questions about SMTs, tool documentation, or the study in general?

We greatly appreciate your time as we understand these were time consuming and possibly confusing tasks. Do you have any final thoughts about your experience today using secret management tools or questions about our study?

<Answer any questions, or continue>

Thank you once again, we would like to remind you that all of your responses and data collected today will remain confidential and de-identified. We will also send compensation shortly after the conclusion of this study session. Thank you, have a great day!